

Spiritual Practice in Workplace and its Psychological Well Being Among Higher Education Faculties

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Abstract

Introduction:

Professors are the heart of every institution; thus, it is more important to develop a flexible teaching force by helping them feel psychologically empowered through link connecting spirituality in workplace and employee engagement between higher educators. This paper aims the study to contribute various disciplines like human resource management, organizational behavior, psychology, and anthropology etc., Conceptual framework have used in this paper. This study is quantitative in nature, well-structured questionnaire has using, and the sample size is 128. This study is only restricted to faculty members in colleges. Three different types of variables have been measured like measuring spiritual practices among faculties in workplace, sense of their meaningful work, psychological well-being, relationship among coworkers finally dedication with their work apart from monetary, awards, and rewards etc. These are the variables most point out in this paper. This study is quantitative in nature, well-structured questionnaire has using, and the sample size is 128. This study is only restricted to faculty members in colleges. The references and reviews of literature are very much relevant and collected from reputed journals. Various implications like academic implications and societal implications have suggested that gives proper evidence for the study.

Objectives:

To determine the elements influencing the level of workplace spirituality and employee engagement among faculty members, and to assess the level of participation among the staff (faculty members) working in the study's participating various organizations.

Results:

Results from validated statistics are 67.18% of respondents were male and 32.82% were female. Hence, women make up most of the responders. majority of academicians have highly satisfied in Spiritual well-being and the highest rating values is 4.25 scores. Second highest value for Ethical Behaviour that observed 4.24 scores. Third highest value for Job Commitment that observed 3.94 scores. Job Satisfaction have 3.92 score values. Wellness lifestyles have 3.92 score values etc...,

Conclusions:

Workplace spirituality has various advantages for the business. Some of the characteristics that characterize spirituality are integrity, honesty, confidence, inner devotion, and self-discipline. In conclusion, employees' spiritual well-being will not only reduce stress, conflict, and absenteeism but also improve wellbeing, quality of life, and work performance and engagement among employees in workplace.

Keywords: Higher Education Academicians, Education, Workplace Spirituality, Spiritual Practice, Psychological Wellbeing, Truthfulness.

1. Introduction

Workplace spirituality is the idea that there is more to life than merely being paid, and that people may find meaning and purpose in their job. It involves a set of morals and principles that help people combine their personal and professional spheres of existence and discover a more fulfilling purpose (Aboobaker, 2019) in their employment. Workplace spirituality focuses on building a feeling of community, a shared sense of purpose, and a commitment to ethical behavior rather than on endorsing any religious doctrine. Employees are encouraged to express their real selves and look for ways to use their profession to positively impact society and the world around them in an office environment that places a strong emphasis on spirituality. This can produce a sense of well-being, job satisfaction, and a pleasant work atmosphere. The subject of spiritual leadership in an organization has been covered in several research. (Mahipalan, 2019) There are organizations that have developed targeted initiatives that support spiritual engagement in the workplace with success. This study investigates the role that spiritual leadership plays in enhancing employee engagement and organizational success. To better understand how spirituality might improve employee performance and increase organizational effectiveness, this study will evaluate the research on the topic. the "spirituality in workplace" refers to these recent developments in organizations that allow for the spiritual component, which has to do with meaning, purpose, and a feeling of community. (Viswanathan, 2019) Recent years have been a continuous rise in interest in organizational spirituality concerns among management experts and corporate managers, according to academics. There is uncertainty on how spirituality affects organizational performance, even though the research and interest in spirituality at work are expanding quickly.

2. Factors affecting workplace spirituality and employee engagement:

- I. Employees are not provided with clear policies and defined duties,
- II. There is a lack of job security and enough wage benefits.
- III. Specified work time does not exist. Torturous job overloads cause stress and poor work-life balance.
- IV. HRM is non-existent, or HR procedures are weak.
- V. There is also too much bossism, which fosters a " You are employed by me, I pay you, therefore follow my instructions. " Mentality.
- VI. Major academic decisions are not made with consultation from the faculty.

3. Conceptual Framework:

To investigate the relationship between spirituality and organizational success, this study intends to contribute to the body of knowledge on the topic. Meditation, mindfulness, introspection, gratitude, and service to others are some activities that might support workplace spirituality. By fostering a feeling of meaning and purpose in one's job, these activities can assist people in developing a connection with both their inner selves and the wider world. Creating a corporate culture that appreciates human potential and promotes a feeling of purpose and wellbeing among employees is the overall goal of workplace spirituality. Organizations may foster a more satisfying and effective working environment for all parties by embracing workplace spirituality.

Employee performance is improved by the established criteria that define employee engagement. Employee accomplishments and success at work affect how well they perform. One of the key elements influencing

employee performance is now widely acknowledged to be employee engagement. Studies show that a company with a greater degree of employee engagement will have employees who perform at a higher level. This demonstrates the importance of workplace spirituality for an employee's capacity for productivity and happiness. If it is acknowledged that seeking out meaningful work within a community, honouring employees' inner lives, and experiencing a sense of connection to others that fills them with joy and fulfilment, then our dimensions indicate spiritual workplace qualities.

4. Need of Workplace Spirituality:

Employee behavior at work should be analyzed from the physical, psychological, and spiritual perspectives for better understanding. Therefore, spirituality is very important in workplace. Although the physical and psychological aspects of people at work have been well researched, the spiritual aspect has languished unexplored for a long time. The need of workplace spirituality are favorable attitude towards work, or job happiness, both are connected. Religion is rigid and founded on traditions, whereas spirituality is adaptable and flexible. Also, while discussing spirituality in the workplace seems to be ok, doing so when discussing religious practice really isn't.

5. Ways to follow Spiritual Practices for happy well-being (work, 2017):

To bring our spirituality to work as people get busier and our lives become progressively more job centric. The recommendations that follow to integrate, practice spirituality and faith at work:

I. Integrate your values into job:

Don't accept a job simply because it pays well and has many advantages. These types of professions might not fit with your moral principles, and it could be challenging to build any kind of workplace spirituality. Instead, pick a profession that reflects your underlying values. Focus your abilities so that you may accomplish job that satisfies your desire to do something good for the world.

II. Think Positively:

You'll be more effective at work and treat people around you better if you can take challenging situations and shed light on them. When discussing the circumstance, try to be constructive. Consider why it is causing you to feel a certain way, then let it go.

III. Be Cheerful with others:

is frequently neglected in work. You should treat others the way you want to be treated. Thank you and please. Let others know you value the job they do. Give praises to people.

IV. Spend some time for self-analysis:

You should treat others the way you want to be treated. Thank you and please. Let others know you value the job they do. Give praises to people. This type of generosity may spread across the office. It will not only improve your outlook but also provide you the chance to make others happy.

V. Good Relationship with our Co-Workers:

Depending on the type of spirituality you follow, concentrate on incorporating activities such as meditation, prayer, or mantras into your workday. You can complete these tasks at your workstation without anybody knowing. These can be little interludes throughout the day that help you reconnect with your spirituality and improve your ability to concentrate at work. Regardless of whether it is a work-related issue or something that is happening in their personal life, getting to know what is important to individuals around you can only be advantageous to the company. If a coworker seems to need someone to chat to, lend them your ear. Your ability to empathize with your coworkers will increase as you learn more about them.

VI. Feel free to giving suggestions about spiritual ideas to our Head:

Bring your supervisor a few concepts you have that fit with the company's principles. Be committed to it. Have a thorough knowledge of the requirements placed on the business and how doing so will benefit both the community and the firm.

VII. Mindfulness:

One of the best ways to carry your spirituality to work with you every day is to practice self-awareness. You will choose decisions that are consistent with your principles if you are completely aware of your words and deeds.

VIII. Creative:

It releases ingrained thought patterns or routines. It makes non-linear thinking possible. Empathy is enabled by creativity. Through connecting with our inner selves, creativity.

IX. Giving priority to our beloved people:

Cultivate connections with everyone in the company. This comprises personnel, clients, and vendors. People desire to remain devoted when they believe that their employer cares about them. The business will benefit greatly from this, but it's also pleasant to be polite.

X. Identify one who understands the spiritual values:

It is always convenient to have a colleague with whom you can exchange ideas. Talk about your faith with your pals you have outside of work if you don't feel comfortable doing so at work. Ask them how they integrate their faith into their employment without upsetting those around them.

XI. Don't urge for immediate results:

When you can, slow down. Be careful in all you say and do, as well as in your decisions and decisions you make. Keep in mind that they all have consequences. Instead, than attempting to multitask, focus on one item at a time. Even when it seems difficult to do so, simply pause for a moment and take a step back. Take many long breaths. It's simpler than you would think to slow down.

XII. Monitor your progress:

Everyone is still learning how to put their values into practice in various real-life scenarios since nobody is flawless. It's quite simple to imagine how you would respond to certain circumstances, but reality generally looks completely different. Regularly evaluate how your ideals are being applied to your spiritual practice at work.

6. Problem Statement:

The main duties of faculties have changed to include teaching and research. It was widely believed that professors who were actively involved in teaching kept their pupils interested, which improved learning. In practice, that is not true. Universities and colleges must engage faculty members to improve student learning to ensure that their work is driven, which in turn inspires students to improve performance. Everything needs to be viewed from a fresh angle. All these call for a novel solution as well as a reference model for more research and to increase workplace spirituality and employee engagement among faculty members. It is crucial to support teachers' involvement at work since, according to prior research, kids pick up on teachers' attitudes and motivation levels. As a result, an initiative has been established to research faculty involvement among faculty members.

7. Review of Literature:

(Reshmi, 2022)The teaching staff is crucial to the success of any educational institution. Together with conventional teaching, online teaching is under stress. They must perform a variety of administrative tasks in addition to teaching. If they become enthusiastic workers, the education they receive will increase. (Janetius, 2016) characterized as the emotional connection and attachment a worker has to their work, coworkers, and organization, which has a significant impact on their level of performance, loyalty, and devotion. The researchers of this study make an educated guess as to whether this notion may be relevant in the educational sector as well because the defining concept and metrics utilized to describe employee engagement solely originate in the educational sector. (Thiruvankadam, 2018) For the improvement of higher education in India, the research offers management of private self-financing schools' information on how to redesign faculty members' jobs and redefine their connections with HODs and institutions. (Nadia, 2023) investigates the connections between social responsibility in business (CSR), spirituality in the workplace (WPS), GPromVB, as well as GProhVB. Data collected from hotel employees and their managers in Northern Cyprus in two waves were used to estimate the

previously mentioned associations using modelling of structural equations. The findings imply that employees' positive perceptions of CSR increase their feelings of WPS, which leads to elevated levels of GPromVB and GProhVB. Finally, WPS acts as a buffer between CSR and GPromVB and GProhVB. Our paper offers implications for industry and academia based on these findings. (Vinodkumar, 2023) Such incidents have been shown to be influenced by factors such as educational qualification, work experience, marriage status, alcohol consumption, and hours spent at work of bus operators. The current study investigates the mediated impact of workplace spirituality (WS) between bus drivers between individual characteristics and job-related variables such as reported accidents, sanctions, and appraisals. (Snehal, 2023) review reveals a scarcity of research on WPS at the mesospiritual level. The findings highlight the potential for cross-cultural studies in WPS to support and advance inclusion and diversity within the organisation. There is also space to investigate the connections between WPS and mental and behavioural health, attitude, creative behaviour, feasible behavior, and trust. Furthermore, the findings highlight the importance of researching the darker aspects of faith in the workplace. (Meena, 2023) investigates the function of resonate leadership (RL) as well as workplace spirituality (WPS) within moderating the constructs, emotional distress (ED), and commitment to organization (OC). The current study uses a design that is exploratory. It employed the method of purposeful sampling to collect data from multiple medical centers in four Indian states that were hardest hit by COVID-19. (Zohu, 2023) To influence essential individual- and team- degree results. Everyone used a newly developed workplace spirituality measure, The Workplace Spirituality Profile on a sample of 331 full-time employees plus an additional 293 members of the team peers, to estimate organizational dedication and team effectiveness, in moral management and willingness of faith environment as facilitators. The findings demonstrated the significance of workplace spirituality for organizational dedication, as well as key moderators of moral management and trust environment openness. Everyone additionally offers a preliminary examination of the factor makeup of the job spirituality measure, completing that nearly all the concept is influenced by an international variable rather than measurements as theorized.

8. Objectives

To determine the elements influencing the level of workplace spirituality and employee engagement among faculty members.

To assess the level of participation among the staff (faculty members) working in the study's participating various organizations.

9. Methodology and Design of Research:

Sampling Technique: Probability sampling technique, Simple random method has been used.

Sample Size: 128 respondents have used for this study.

Data Collections: The current study uses primary data and is a cross-sectional descriptive study. The main information was gathered from colleges with locations in Salem. Structured questionnaire was used, along with literature reviews and faculty interviews at various educational institutions. Data from papers, journals, periodicals, and magazines written by practitioners are used as secondary source. Analysis and Interpretation's: Tables and Charts have used

Data Analysis:

A. Sex of the Respondents:

Table:1

Sex	Respondents	Percentage
Male	86	67.18
Female	42	32.82
Total	128	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

According to the above-mentioned statistics, 67.18% of respondents were male and 32.82% were female. Hence, women make up most of the responders.

Chart:1

B. Weighted average

Table 2

S:NO	PARTICULARS	Highly Satisfied	Satis-Fied	Neutral	Dis Satisfied	Highly Dis Satisfied	Total	Values
		5	4	3	2	1	Average / no.of respondents	
1	Spiritual Well Being	255	248	36	6	0	545/128	4.25
2	Ethical Behaviour	150	272	75	6	2	505/128	3.94
3	Job Commitment	120	260	105	6	1	492/128	3.84
4	Job Satisfaction	180	212	99	12	0	503/128	3.92
5	Wellness Lifestyle	135	192	126	12	5	470/128	3.67
6	Connectedness	310	160	66	6	1	543/128	4.24

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

In the above weighted average table, researcher had found that majority of academicians have highly satisfied in Spiritual well-being and the highest rating values is 4.25 scores. Second highest value for Ethical Behaviour that observed 4.24 scores. Third highest value for Job Commitment that observed 3.94 scores. Job Satisfaction have 3.92 score values. Wellness lifestyles have 3.92 score values. And Connectedness have least score values 3.67 in the table.

Chart:2

C. ANOVA

Table 3

H0: There is no significant relationship between the workers in organization.

S.No	Variable	Category	Frequency	Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
1	Age	Below 25 Years	19.0000	Between Groups	28.814	5	5.763	.469	.799	NS
		26-35 Years	19.0200							
		36-45 Years	20.6665	With in Groups	1621.87		12.282			
		46 Years and above	19.4532							
2	Department	Arts	18.7788	Between Groups	45.454	8	32.56	.358	.005	S
		Science	17.5785							
		Commerce	20.4875	With in Groups	1587.6		10.56			
		Education	16.4532							

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The P value for (Age and Department) is larger than (0.05), as shown in the above table, and the null hypothesis is accepted at the 5% level of significance. The results are significant at the 5% level, indicating that there is no discernible difference between faculty members' overall perceptions of and inner attitudes towards intuition. The above table also demonstrates that the P value for department and age is less than 0.05, rejecting the null hypothesis (Ho). So, it may be concluded that there are notable differences between employees' general impressions of situations and their internal attitudes about perception.

10. Discussion

The employer benefits financially as well as by building a more dependable and contented team that having a humane work atmosphere benefits the company and its workers alike. Workplace spirituality has various advantages for the business. Some of the characteristics that characterize spirituality are integrity, honesty,

confidence, inner devotion, and self-discipline. In conclusion, employees' spiritual well-being will not only reduce stress, conflict, and absenteeism but also improve wellbeing, quality of life, and work performance and engagement among employees in workplace. This is because when people work with a committed spirit, they can find a sense of meaning and purpose, as well as a sense of fulfilment, at work.

11. Implications of the Study

Academic Implication:

The educational sector may influence culture through fostering spirituality in the workplace. They ought to offer various types of meditation, spiritual talks, and integrity for other religions and sects. People will be able to communicate the truth and have confidence in one another thanks to such training, which will make the workplace more spiritual and improve sudden cultural shift. Increased trust will thus lead to greater job satisfaction. Positive effects can be seen, such as greater dedication to and engagement at work, as well as decreased attrition and absenteeism. The education sector will aid them in providing a concept about their task performance, which must be accomplished first, and which must be in the end, by emphasizing on the existence of workplace spirituality. It would ultimately force them to be at work on time and even manage their work volume. Having principles that are connected to the spiritual building can promote trust among coworkers and makes the employees more honest in their values and actions.

Societal Implications:

This survey has confirmed previous studies indicating individuals in the various companies/institutions are seeking more fulfilling and goal-oriented work, as well as a sense of community and support from their coworkers. Owing to the interconnected spiritual ideals, both parties—the company and the employees—will pursue mutual trust, resulting in advantages for both the organization and the individuals also to create engagement among employees.

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